

Supplementary appendix S1: search strategy in different databases

Pubmed

1. Depression[MeSH Terms]
2. Depression[Title/Abstract]
3. Depressions[Title/Abstract]
4. Depressive Symptoms[Title/Abstract]
5. Depressive Symptom[Title/Abstract]
6. Symptom, Depressive[Title/Abstract]
7. Symptoms, Depressive[Title/Abstract]
8. Emotional Depression[Title/Abstract]
9. Depression, Emotional[Title/Abstract]
10. Depressions, Emotional[Title/Abstract]
11. Emotional Depressions[Title/Abstract]
12. OR 1-11
13. Depressive Disorder[MeSH Terms]
14. Depressive Disorder[Title/Abstract]
15. Depressive Disorders[Title/Abstract]
16. Disorder, Depressive[Title/Abstract]
17. Disorders, Depressive[Title/Abstract]
18. Neurosis, Depressive[Title/Abstract]
19. Depressive Neuroses[Title/Abstract]
20. Depressive Neurosis[Title/Abstract]
21. Neuroses, Depressive[Title/Abstract]
22. Depression, Endogenous[Title/Abstract]
23. Depressions, Endogenous[Title/Abstract]
24. Endogenous Depression[Title/Abstract]
25. Endogenous Depressions[Title/Abstract]
26. Depressive Syndrome[Title/Abstract]
27. Depressive Syndromes[Title/Abstract]
28. Syndrome, Depressive[Title/Abstract]
29. Syndromes, Depressive[Title/Abstract]
30. Depression, Neurotic[Title/Abstract]
31. Depressions, Neurotic[Title/Abstract]
32. Neurotic Depression[Title/Abstract]
33. Neurotic Depressions[Title/Abstract]
34. Melancholia[Title/Abstract]
35. Melancholias[Title/Abstract]
36. Unipolar Depression[Title/Abstract]
37. Depression, Unipolar[Title/Abstract]
38. Depressions, Unipolar[Title/Abstract]
39. Depressions, Unipolar[Title/Abstract]
40. 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16 OR 17 OR 18 OR 19 OR 20 OR 21 OR 22 OR 23 OR 24 OR 25 OR 26 OR 27 OR 28 OR 29 OR 30 OR 31 OR 32 OR 33 OR 34 OR 35 OR 36 OR 37 OR 38 OR

41. 12 OR 40
42. Acupuncture[MeSH Terms]
43. Acupuncture[Title/Abstract]
44. 42 OR 43
45. Acupuncture Therapy[MeSH Terms]
46. Acupuncture Therapy[Title/Abstract]
47. Acupuncture Treatment[Title/Abstract]
48. Acupuncture Treatments[Title/Abstract]
49. Treatment, Acupuncture[Title/Abstract]
50. Therapy, Acupuncture[Title/Abstract]
51. 45 OR 46 OR 47 OR 48 OR 49 OR 50
52. Acupuncture Points[MeSH Terms]
53. Acupuncture Points[Title/Abstract]
54. Acupuncture Point[Title/Abstract]
55. Point, Acupuncture[Title/Abstract]
56. Points, Acupuncture[Title/Abstract]
57. Acupoints[Title/Abstract]
58. Acupoint[Title/Abstract]
59. 52 OR 53 OR 54 OR 55 OR 56 OR 57 OR 58
60. Electroacupuncture[MeSH Terms]
61. Electroacupuncture[Title/Abstract]
62. 60 OR 61
63. 44 OR 51 OR 59 OR 62
64. randomized controlled trial[Publication Type]
65. controlled clinical trial[Publication Type]
66. Clinical Trial[Publication Type]
67. randomized controlled trials as Topic[MeSH Terms]
68. controlled clinical trials as Topic[MeSH Terms]
69. Clinical Trials as Topic[MeSH Terms]
70. randomized controlled trial[Title/Abstract]
71. controlled clinical trial[Title/Abstract]
72. RCT[Title/Abstract]
73. CCT[Title/Abstract]
74. randomized[Title/Abstract]
75. randomly[Title/Abstract]
76. trial[Title/Abstract]
77. 64 OR 65 OR 66 OR 67 OR 68 OR 69 OR 70 OR 71 OR 72 OR 73 OR 74 OR 75 OR 76
78. 41 AND 63 AND 77
79. animals[MeSH Terms]
80. humans[MeSH Terms]
81. 79 NOT 80
82. 78 NOT 81

Embase

- #1 'depression'/exp
- #2 depression:ab,ti
- #3 'central depression':ab,ti
- #4 'clinical depression':ab,ti
- #5 'depressive disease':ab,ti
- #6 'depressive disorder':ab,ti
- #7 'depressive episode':ab,ti
- #8 'depressive illness':ab,ti
- #9 'depressive personality disorder':ab,ti
- #10 'depressive state':ab,ti
- #11 'depressive symptom':ab,ti
- #12 'depressive syndrome':ab,ti
- #13 'mental depression':ab,ti
- #14 #1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11 OR #12 OR #13
- #15 acupuncture'/exp
- #16 acupuncture:ab,ti
- #17 'acupuncture therapy':ab,ti
- #18 #15 OR #16 OR #17
- #19 'acupuncture points'/exp
- #20 'acupuncture points':ab,ti
- #21 'acu point':ab,ti
- #22 acupoint:ab,ti
- #23 acupoints:ab,ti
- #24 'point, acupuncture':ab,ti
- #25 #19 OR #20 OR #21 OR #22 OR #23 OR #24
- #26 'electroacupuncture'/exp
- #27 electroacupuncture:ab,ti
- #28 'acupuncture, electric':ab,ti
- #29 'electric acupuncture':ab,ti
- #30 'electrical acupoint stimulation':ab,ti
- #31 'electrical acupuncture':ab,ti
- #32 'electro acupuncture':ab,ti
- #33 'electrode acupuncture':ab,ti
- #34 'electronic acupuncture':ab,ti
- #35 #26 OR #27 OR #28 OR #29 OR #30 OR #31 OR #32 OR #33 OR #34
- #36 #18 OR #25 OR #35
- #37 'randomized controlled trial'/exp
- #38 'randomized controlled trial topic'/exp
- #39 'controlled clinical trial'/exp
- #40 'controlled clinical trial topic'/exp
- #41 'clinical trial'/exp
- #42 'clinical trial topic'/exp
- #43 'randomized controlled trial':ab,ti

#44 'controlled clinical trial':ab,ti

#45 rct:ab,ti

#46 cct:ab,ti

#47 randomly:ab,ti

#48 randomized:ab,ti

#49 trial:ab,ti

#50 #37 OR #38 OR #39 OR #40 OR #41 OR #42 OR #43 OR #44 OR #45 OR #46 OR #47 OR
#48 OR #49

#51 #14 AND #36 AND #50

#52 'animal'/exp

#53 'human'/exp

#54 #52 NOT #53

#55 #51 NOT #54

Cochrane library

- #1 MeSH descriptor: [Depression] explode all trees
- #2 (Depression):ti,ab,kw
- #3 (Depressions):ti,ab,kw
- #4 (Depressive Symptoms):ti,ab,kw
- #5 (Emotional Depression):ti,ab,kw
- #6 (Depressive Symptom):ti,ab,kw
- #7 (Symptoms, Depressive):ti,ab,kw
- #8 (Symptom, Depressive):ti,ab,kw
- #9 (Emotional Depressions):ti,ab,kw
- #10 (Depressions, Emotional):ti,ab,kw
- #11 (Depression, Emotional):ti,ab,kw
- #12 #1 OR #2 OR #3 OR #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8 OR #9 OR #10 OR #11
- #13 MeSH descriptor: [Depressive Disorder] explode all trees
- #14 (Depressive Disorder):ti,ab,kw
- #15 (Depressions, Unipolar):ti,ab,kw
- #16 (Depression, Unipolar):ti,ab,kw
- #17 (Unipolar Depressions):ti,ab,kw
- #18 (Unipolar Depression):ti,ab,kw
- #19 (Neuroses, Depressive):ti,ab,kw
- #20 (Depressive Neuroses):ti,ab,kw
- #21 (Depressive Disorders):ti,ab,kw
- #22 (Disorder, Depressive):ti,ab,kw
- #23 (Neurosis, Depressive):ti,ab,kw
- #24 (Disorders, Depressive):ti,ab,kw
- #25 (Depressive Neurosis):ti,ab,kw
- #26 (Endogenous Depression):ti,ab,kw
- #27 (Depressions, Endogenous):ti,ab,kw
- #28 (Endogenous Depressions):ti,ab,kw
- #29 (Depression, Endogenous):ti,ab,kw
- #30 (Melancholia):ti,ab,kw
- #31 (Melancholias):ti,ab,kw
- #32 (Neurotic Depression):ti,ab,kw
- #33 (Neurotic Depressions):ti,ab,kw
- #34 (Depressions, Neurotic):ti,ab,kw
- #35 (Depression, Neurotic):ti,ab,kw
- #36 (Depressive Syndromes):ti,ab,kw
- #37 (Depressive Syndrome):ti,ab,kw
- #38 (Syndromes, Depressive):ti,ab,kw
- #39 (Syndrome, Depressive):ti,ab,kw
- #40 #13 OR #14 OR #15 OR #16 OR #17 OR #18 OR #19 OR #20 OR #21 OR #22 OR #23 OR
#24 OR #25 OR #26 OR #27 OR #28 OR #29 OR #30 OR #31 OR #32 OR #33 OR #34 OR
#35 OR #36 OR #37 OR #38 OR #39
- #41 #12 OR #40

#42 MeSH descriptor: [Acupuncture] explode all trees
#43 (Acupuncture):ti,ab,kw
#44 #42 OR #43
#45 MeSH descriptor: [Acupuncture Therapy] explode all trees
#46 (Acupuncture Therapy):ti,ab,kw
#47 (Treatment, Acupuncture):ti,ab,kw
#48 (Acupuncture Treatments):ti,ab,kw
#49 (Acupuncture Treatment):ti,ab,kw
#50 (Therapy, Acupuncture):ti,ab,kw
#51 (Acupotomy):ti,ab,kw
#52 (Acupotomies):ti,ab,kw
#53 #45 OR #46 OR #47 OR #48 OR #49 OR #50 OR #51 OR #52
#54 MeSH descriptor: [Acupuncture Points] explode all trees
#55 (Acupuncture Points):ti,ab,kw
#56 (Acupoint):ti,ab,kw
#57 (Acupoints):ti,ab,kw
#58 (Points, Acupuncture):ti,ab,kw
#59 (Point, Acupuncture):ti,ab,kw
#60 (Acupuncture Point):ti,ab,kw
#61 #54 OR #55 OR #56 OR #57 OR #58 OR #59 OR #60
#62 MeSH descriptor: [Electroacupuncture] explode all trees
#63 (Electroacupuncture):ti,ab,kw
#64 #62 OR #63
#65 #44 OR #53 OR #61 OR #64
#66 (randomized controlled trial):pt
#67 (controlled clinical trial):pt
#68 (clinical trial):pt
#69 MeSH descriptor: [Randomized Controlled Trial] explode all trees
#70 MeSH descriptor: [Controlled Clinical Trial] explode all trees
#71 MeSH descriptor: [Clinical Trial] explode all trees
#72 MeSH descriptor: [Randomized Controlled Trials as Topic] explode all trees
#73 MeSH descriptor: [Controlled Clinical Trials as Topic] explode all trees
#74 MeSH descriptor: [Clinical Trials as Topic] explode all trees
#75 (randomized controlled trial):ti,ab,kw
#76 (controlled clinical trial):ti,ab,kw
#77 (RCT):ti,ab,kw
#78 (CCT):ti,ab,kw
#79 (randomized):ti,ab,kw
#80 (randomly):ti,ab,kw
#81 (trial):ti,ab,kw
#82 #66 OR #67 OR #68 OR #69 OR #70 OR #71 OR #72 OR #73 OR #74 OR #75 OR #76 OR
#77 OR #78 OR #79 OR #80 OR #81
#83 #41 AND #65 AND #82

Web of Science

- #1 TS=(Depression OR Depressions OR Depressive Symptoms OR Depressive Symptom OR Symptom, Depressive OR Symptoms, Depressive OR Emotional Depression OR Depression, Emotional OR Depressions, Emotional OR Emotional Depressions)
- #2 TS=(Depressive Disorder OR Depressive Disorders OR Disorder, Depressive OR Disorders, Depressive OR Neurosis, Depressive OR Depressive Neuroses OR Depressive Neurosis OR Neuroses, Depressive OR Depression, Endogenous OR Depressions, Endogenous OR Endogenous Depression OR Endogenous Depressions OR Depressive Syndrome OR Depressive Syndromes OR Syndrome, Depressive OR Syndromes, Depressive OR Depression, Neurotic OR Depressions, Neurotic OR Neurotic Depression OR Neurotic Depressions OR Melancholia OR Melancholias OR Unipolar Depression OR Depression, Unipolar OR Depressions, Unipolar OR Unipolar Depressions)
- #3 #1 OR #2
- #4 TS=(Acupuncture)
- #5 TS=(Acupuncture Therapy OR Acupuncture Treatment OR Acupuncture Treatments OR Treatment, Acupuncture OR Therapy, Acupuncture)
- #6 TS=(Acupuncture Points OR Acupuncture Point OR Point, Acupuncture OR Points, Acupuncture OR Acupoints OR Acupoint)
- #7 TS=(Electroacupuncture)
- #8 #4 OR #5 OR #6 OR #7
- #9 TS=(randomized controlled trial OR controlled clinical trial OR RCT OR CCT OR randomized OR randomly OR trial)
- #10 #3 AND #8 AND #9